

WITH CREATIVITY TO SUSTAINABLE INNOVATION – LEGO® SERIOUS PLAY®

Identify new ways of sustainable transformation,
process optimisation and resource efficiency in your company

WHAT IS LEGO®SERIOUS PLAY® (LSP)?

LEGO® Serious Play® is a **facilitated workshop method** that uses LEGO bricks as a tool for creative thinking, problem solving and communication.

Designed to promote group discussions and develop the full potential of participants, LEGO® Serious Play® supports the visualisation and explanation of complex topics.

Through interactive engagement, the method helps to create a common level of knowledge.

WHAT ARE THE ADVANTAGES OF LEGO®SERIOUS PLAY®?

- Improved communication: Visualise and share complex ideas in a casual environment to deepen understanding.
- Closer cooperation: Promote active listening by involving everyone and encourage diverse perspectives for improved collaboration.
- Creative problem-solving: LEGO® Serious Play® stimulates creative thinking in order to break through conventional thought patterns.
- Improved decision-making: Explore scenarios from a bird's eye view for a common basis for decision-making.

HOW CAN LSP SUPPORT SUSTAINABLE TRANSFORMATION?

LEGO® Serious Play® provides a unique perspective on the transformation of industry. Visual representations make complex relationships more understandable, while the interactive approach opens up creative optimisation possibilities. This includes the improvement of interactions, processes and workflows, which not only increases efficiency but also generates cost savings.

Did we spark your interest?
Arrange an initial consultation appointment with the NEFI team!

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